

GENDER ISSUES IN MANAGEMENT

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senior teacher **Annotation** The article deals with the problem of gender differences and examines gender differences in management. This article defines the concept of gender psychology.

Keywords: gender psychology, gene, gender, gender, socialization, prejudice, discrimination, social perception, self-perception, self-esteem, differentiation, leader.

Introduction

Currently, due to the drastic changes in economic, political and social conditions, the issues of sexual differentiation are becoming especially relevant, since they have always been closely linked with socio-economic life, and abrupt changes in society have led to a change in views on the problem of gender and gender relations.

The relevance of this article of the mental, behavioral characteristics of male and female managers in the decision-making process is associated not only with theoretical, but also with applied aspects of psychology and is determined by the following reasons.

Firstly, the importance that studies of the subjective determinants of personality behavior, including the head, acquire today as a factor of influence on the decision-making situation in the organizational and production environment.

Secondly, the importance of these problems is currently increasing due to the increase in the number of women in management structures at various levels, the number of decisions they make in politics, economics, public life is growing, which creates the need for knowledge of their personal characteristics in the regulation of behavior and professional activity.

Thirdly, it is impossible not to say about the purely practical significance and interest in various fields of professional activity, including managerial, to the gender and age-related aspects of human behavior (including the decision-making process) that determine its effectiveness. In this regard, the relevance of studying the processes of decision-making by managers, mediated by individual personal, gender and age differences, is significantly increased.

Gender psychology is a branch of differential psychology that studies the patterns of human behavior in society determined by his biological sex, social sex (gender) and their relationship.[1]

Gender studies of social psychology study such phenomena as: socialization, prejudice, discrimination, social perception and self-perception, self-esteem, the emergence of social norms and roles.

There are several main directions in gender psychology:

The psychology of comparing men and women is the study of the specific characteristics of men and women, in establishing the uniqueness of the sexes.

- Psychology of women — the study of the characteristics of a woman's mental state related to female physiology, which men do not have.
- Male psychology — the study of the characteristics of a man's mental state related to male physiology, which women do not have.
- Gender socialization — the study of the formation of gender identity and the development of gender roles.
- Psychology of gender relations — consideration of relationships both between the sexes and within the same sex.

- Gender Psychology of leadership — the study of differences between male leaders and female leaders, as well as dominance-subordination relationships.
- Gender psychology in sports is a field of gender psychology and sports psychology that studies the features and differences of sports activities in connection with the gender and gender identity of an athlete or team.[2] **Results and discussion**

Studies of gender differences are presented in domestic and foreign psychology by a set of scientific developments on relationships in different-sex collectives, which can be reduced to two main areas: studies of the influence of the representation of different sexes in a group on their relationships (R. Canter, A. Eskilson, M. Wilson, R. Hagen, A. Kan, O. A. Kostinikova, V. I. Gushchin, Yu. N. Guryanov) and studies of gender-based conflicts (O'Neill, M. Horner, K. West, D. Zimmerman, E. Igli, O. A. Gavrilitsa, N. N. Korostyleva, etc.). In management activities, taking into account the gender characteristics of the head is one of the most important tasks of psychological support of the efficiency of modern printing organizations.

However, currently in management psychology there is no unified theory of gender differences in management, defining a set of gender characteristics manifested in the managerial activities of managers engaged in the field of printing, the structure and content of the concept of gender in management are not defined, as well as the impact of these differences on the effectiveness of their managerial activities, a system of training managers for effective management activities.

The state and degree of development of the research problem. Quite a large number of studies have been devoted to psychological problems of the decisionmaking process in the activities of the head (V.A. Abchuk, A.G. Wendelin, V.V. Golubinov, V.V. Grigolava, D.N. Zavalishina, A.N. Ivanova, A.B. Karpov, Yu. Kozeletsky, T.V. Kornilova, V.V. Kochetkov, I. Khol, O.I. Larichev, B.F. Lomov, E.V. Markova, V.F. Rubakhin, I.G. Skotiikova, L.N. Sumarokov, A.B. Filippov and many others. others), which confirm that decision-making (related and not related to risk) depends not only on the situational context, but also on individual and personal

factors. However, it must be recognized that the description of the characteristics of the behavior of male and female managers in the decision-making process is somewhat vague and mainly affects the stylistic features of decision-making in risk conditions. Meanwhile, this is a very important and urgent problem of modern practical psychology that requires more detailed study. Accordingly, the purpose of our research is to identify and study the gender characteristics of the personality of the head in the management of an enterprise, organization.

There are quite a large number of factors that influence the gender–role socialization of an individual. Special cultural techniques that promote the consolidation of "male" and "female" identities include education, public opinion, works of literature and art, advertising, mass media, television, etc. All this arsenal of tools is aimed at reproducing traditional ideas about the roles of men and women, and thereby maintaining and reproducing these norms. Traditional ideas about the roles of men and women are based on the assertion that their social behavior is caused by biological differences. "Anatomy is fate," the famous psychoanalyst Sigmund Freud argued at the beginning of the twentieth century. The upbringing of boys is traditionally aggressive in nature, since a man should be stronger, more energetic and more aggressive than a woman. Men are given the role of creators of history and culture. From childhood, girls are offered the role of a future mother, who should not have personal interests, but should devote her life to her family - her husband and children. From a young age, girls are instilled with the idea of their certain inferiority, the idea of lifelong dependence on a man is inspired. Girls are brought up both physically and psychologically defenseless, which becomes a favorable factor in accepting violence against themselves. Women are assigned the role of housewives, who are entrusted to do housework and raising children. Such a biologically determined (deterministic) approach to male and female roles is now being criticized by supporters of the idea of social construction of gender.

The term "sex" describes biological differences between people determined by genetic features of the structure of cells, anatomical and physiological characteristics and reproductive functions.

The term "gender" indicates the social status and socio-psychological characteristics of a person that are related to gender and sexuality, but arise in interaction with other people. That is, gender is a kind of social gender. Thus, sex is the biological status of a person, and gender is a socio-psychological status, the formation of which is influenced by a variety of socio-cultural factors. Representatives of the so-called "new psychology of sex" (J. Stokkard, M. Johnson, S. Bem) argue that the biological, innate sex only helps to determine the potential behavior of a person, and the main, significant is the psychological, social gender, which is assimilated in life.

In psychology, two divergent positions regarding the root cause of gender differences are clearly distinguished. Some authors emphasize the determining role of the biological factor in the formation of these differences (T.P. Khrizman, V.D. Ereemeeva, V.A. Geodakyan, S.I. Kudinov, A. Pease, A.L. Sirotyuk, etc.), others – the social factor (J. Lorber and S. Farrell, K. West and D. Zimmerman, S.V. Ushakin, V.N. Kunitsyna, M.V. Burakova, N.K. Radina, L.N. Ozhigova, G.V. Turk, etc.). Proponents of the biological determination of gender differences believe that the psychological differences between men and women are nothing but a continuation of biological differences. The foundation for the development of future men and women are genetically laid prerequisites on the basis of which sex is formed, and the social factor is secondary.

Conclusion

In a psychological sense, behavior primarily includes motives, goals, value orientations and means that transform the possibilities given by nature into certain actions. And motives, goals, value orientations and means are associated with the impact of culture and society on a person. Society determines the means and limits of the manifestation of the activity of the organism. Culture provides a system of

signs through which a person designates his natural qualities, gives them a certain meaning. Consequently, culture is an organizing principle and a system-forming feature of behavior, which we designate as male or female. In other words, it is the cultural definitions of individual human qualities and abilities that serve as the basis for the classification of male, female or neutral (that is, characteristic of both sexes) traits. Often, the characteristics of biological activity are confused with behavior in a socio-psychological sense. The mixing of sexual and gender characteristics leads to the fact that the characteristics of masculinity and femininity simultaneously include both psychophysiological and socio-cultural aspects of psychological differences, whereas in situations of real interaction between people rarely associate the biological characteristics of their body with gender characteristics. The mixing of gender and gender differences is often used to criticize the gender approach to explaining people's behavior.

From all of the above, it can be concluded that both male and female managers have their own valuable qualities necessary for making effective managerial decisions. Despite the fact that men and women have different styles of management, behavior and thinking, they can achieve the same effective results, but only in different ways.

REFERENCES:

1. Гендерная психология / Берн Ш. М. *The Social Psychology of Gender*, в переводе Л. Царук, М. Моисеева, О. Боголюбовой // СПб.: Прайм-Еврознак, 2004. — 320 с. ISBN 593878-125-6 в переводе (ISBN 0-07-009182-X оригинала).
2. Филатова А. Ф. Психология половых различий и гендерная психология Архивная копия от 21 февраля 2022 на Wayback Machine / УДК 159.922.2 // «Вестник Омского университета». 2007, № 1. ISSN 1812-3996. — С. 125-130.
3. Kamolov D. R. O. G. L. O'ZBEKISTONDA DEMOKRATIYA VA AXLOQNING ZAMONAVIY MUAMMOLARI VA YECHIMLARI // Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. NUU Conference 2. – С. 348-352.
4. Kamolov, D. (2021). *ATHENIAN DEMOCRACY: INDIVIDUAL AND COLLECTIVE FREEDOM*. [Semantic Scholar](#).

5. Ra'no Munarova, Абдумуминова Махлиё Окмирза кизи, СЕМЕЙНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ В РОМАНЕ ЛЬВА НИКОЛАЕВИЧА ТОЛСТОГО «АННА КАРЕНИНА», Журнал Педагогики и психологии в современном образовании: Том 2 № 5 (2022): Журнал педагогики и психологии в современном образовании
6. Kamolov, D. (2021). Davlat boshqaruviga oid axloqiy qarashlar. Адабиёт учқунлари.
7. Munarova, R. (2022). ПРОБЛЕМЫ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНОГО ВОСПИТАНИЯ МОЛОДОГО ПОКОЛЕНИЯ. Журнал Педагогики и психологии в современном образовании, 2(5). извлечено от <https://ppmedu.jspi.uz/index.php/ppmedu/article/view/5097>
8. Bolibekova, M., Nematov, O., & Nematova, F. (2021). Maxim of politeness in uzbek and english language. Theoretical & applied science Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука, (10), 510-515.